

Humma (Fever) In Unani Medicine: Conceptual Framework, Classification, Pathophysiological, And Therapeutic Insights

Iliyas Hussain^{1*}, Junaid Malik Hashmi², Mohd Zulkifle³

¹*Assistant professor, Department of Kulliyat, Hayat Unani Medical College & Research Center, Lucknow 226101.

²P.G. Scholar Department of Kulliyat, State Unani Medical College, Prayagraj, 211006

³HoD Department of Kulliyat-e-Tib, National Institute of Unani Medicine, Bengaluru. 560091

ABSTRACT

Humma (fever) is a significant pathological condition in Unani medicine, characterized by a disturbance in the body's innate heat (Harārat Gharīziyya) and humoral balance. This research explores the pathophysiology, classification, and therapeutic approaches of various types of Humma, including Humma al-Yawm, Humma Khiltiyya, Humma Ufuniyya, and Humma Diqqiyya, based on classical Unani texts. The study examines the etiological factors such as emotional disturbances, external stimuli, and infections affecting different humors (Akhlat). It highlights the role of Tabi'at (the regulating faculty) in maintaining thermal equilibrium and responding to pathological changes. Treatment principles (Usool-e-'Ilāj) emphasize elimination of causes, strengthening of vital forces, dietary regulation, regimen measures, and pharmacotherapy tailored to individual Mizāj (temperament). The findings underscore the depth and relevance of Unani understanding of fevers, presenting a holistic model of diagnosis and management that aligns with both traditional wisdom and contemporary clinical insights. Methodology: This research follows a qualitative and analytical approach, grounded in classical Unani literature. The primary method involved an extensive review of authoritative Unani texts such as Al-Qānūn fī al-Ṭibb by Ibn Sīnā, Kāmil al-Ṣanā'a by Ali Ibn Abbas Majusi, Zakhīra Khwārizm Shāhī by Jurjānī, Kitāb al-Mukhtārāt fil-Ṭibb by Ibn Hubal Baghdadi, and Firdaus-ul-Hikmat by Rabban Tabari. Supplementary references were drawn from recognized Unani compilations like Kulliyāt-e-Nafisi, Kulliyāt-e-Asri, and Mabādi' yat-e-Ṭibb. The content related to the definition, classification, causes, and treatment of various forms of Humma was extracted and thematically analyzed. The study focused on understanding the pathophysiology of Humma in terms of humoral imbalances, disturbances in innate heat (Harārat Gharīziyya), and the role of Tabi'at in disease progression and resolution. The extracted information was categorized into different types of fevers, such as Humma al-Yawm, Humma Khiltiyya, Humma Ufuniyya, and Humma Diqqiyya. A correlative analysis was conducted to compare and contextualize these Unani descriptions with modern medical insights on fever, thermoregulation, infection, and systemic responses. The therapeutic principles (Usool-e-'Ilāj) were also analyzed, focusing on dietotherapy, regimenal therapy, and pharmacotherapy, with detailed references to classical prescriptions and therapeutic guidelines based on individual mizāj (temperament) and the severity of the fever. Relevant content from recent Unani research papers, dissertations, and academic publications was reviewed to strengthen the contemporary relevance of the subject. All citations were documented with appropriate page numbers from the original or translated sources to ensure academic rigor and traceability. This integrated approach provided a comprehensive understanding of Humma from the traditional Unani framework while aligning with modern clinical interpretations

Keywords: Humma, Fever, Unani Medicine, Hararat Gharīziyya, Usool-e-'Ilāj, Tabi'at.

INTRODUCTION

Hummā is a pathological condition of human beings where the temperature of the human body increases moderately. Hummā is referred to as bukhār in the

general Indian language, and in Persian it is referred to as Tāp^{1, 21}. It is vital for the survival of the human body that the different functions available in the body are performed properly. Hummā refers to a state that

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is produced when the heat generated and heat lost in the body become greater for any reason. A normal has been established for the physiological temperature of the body²¹. Normal body temperature is between 36.5 to 37.5°C (or 97.7 to 99.5°F)^{59, 61}. Whenever the body temperature rises, irrespective of whether the reason lies within or outside the body, "outside the body" implies sunbathing, consumption of hot food and drugs, bathing in hot water, etc. In this manner, we can realize that when someone bathes with hot water, the body is warmed up by the warmth of the water, yet the water is cooled by the coldness of the body. It cools more than before since it absorbs less heat from the body upon meeting the body. These are not as severe in cause; the internal causes are those which occur within the human body. For instance, Fāsīd Mādā (Mawad), Sudda, etc.²¹

The heat that occurs in the body is referred to as Hararat Gharīziyya. Hararat Gharīziyya is the heat that is naturally or at birth acquired by every human being. Hararat Gharīziyya is linked with Ruṭūbat Gharīziyya. Harārat Gharīziyya is acquired by a human being during the union of sperm and ovum³, and this heat is preserved in the body, and Harārat Gharīziyya actually carries out all the activities of the body, such as Afal Nafsāniyya (psychic functions), Afal Haywāniyya (vital functions), and Afal Tab'iyya (natural functions).^{15,49} The body consists of various kinds of Arkan^{10,56}, and all the time there is disturbance taking place in the body because of which heat is always being produced in the body and is also being lost⁹.

Harārat Gharīziyya is synonymous with "real body heat." If Hararat Gharīziyya rises moderately, it is known as Hararat Gharība^{2, 10}. Such heat disturbs the bodily functions.^{15,21} Production and expenditure of heat within the body is regulated by Tabiat mudabira badan. Whereas when our body's temperature rises for any reason, it is Tabi'at which makes it come down, hence the man becomes thirsty for cold water due to the hararat being decreased by the burudat. In the same way, our body, ducts, and all parts of our bodies continuously give out different amounts of vapor. And at times sweat is released quite a lot, so besides evaporation and sweat, body heat is also lost due to excretion of waste products that are heated by the body heat, e.g., urine, faeces, etc.²¹

External cause fever disappears rapidly and does not do much harm to the body since it is not so strong that it can influence the body's functions. Consequently, fever results from these causes and is referred to as humma al-yawm (ephemeral fever)/Ekroza tap (single-day fever), which disappears within 24 hours or within 3 days^{20, 22, 28, 31, 45}.

Definition: Fever is a body temperature that is abnormally high due to the heart or some other cause, can occur in any other organ, then be passed on to the heart, and from the heart, Rūh and blood carries it all over the body. In the body, this abnormal temperature disrupts normal originating functions and even deranges them^{11, 21, 31, 48, 22}. Fever is an abnormal temperature, which is generated by the heart and carried to the entire body.^{2, 4}. Ali Ibne Abbas Majusi has mentioned fever as "a disease caused by Sū'i-mizaj Gārm". A fever accompanied by a lārzā (shiver). Another fever is accompanied by Tākāssur (body pain).⁴⁸

Classification of Humma (Fever): Humma (Fever) is divided into three categories based on these three elements of the body.^{14, 18, 28, 45, 20, 34, 42, 58}

1. Humma al-yawm – about Ruh (pneuma)
2. Humma Khiltiyya – about Akhlat (humours)
3. Humma diqqiyya – about A'dā' Aṣliyya (organ/tissues)

Humma al-yawm (Ephemeral/single-day fever):

The main cause of Humma al-yawm is Asbāb Badiya (external causes)^{11, 14, 45}. Asbāb Badiya has an internal or external impact on hararat gharīziyya⁷. The hararat gharīziyya advances towards the outer body or inner body after being influenced by Asbab bādiya. Motility of hararat gharīziyya can be in either direction, could be slow or rapid.⁶ Hararat Gharīziyya moves rapidly towards the exterior of the body as happens in the anger stage. Consequently, the face turns red immediately, the eyes pop out, and blood vessels become evident⁴. In happiness, harārat gharīziyya slowly moves towards the exterior of the body.⁶

Likewise, hararat gharīziyya shifts suddenly within the body, as with a fear state. And hararat gharīziyya progresses slowly towards the interior of the body, as

in a state of bereavement,⁶ Because hararat gharīziyya moves to surface or center of the body the Rūh (pneuma) gets heated, and on this heat's reaching the heart, it heats the heart and the arteries, and through the arteries, this heat spread everywhere in the body and causes fever. The Hararat Gharīziyya movement can be explained as follows: when something happens before a person that is not acceptable to the individual. If there happens to be an accident or something fearful or something tragic, etc., then the Harārat gharīziyya departs in a radial direction.

External causes for humma al-yawm influence the human body in various ways. Either they are affected by Infi'ālāt Nafsaniyya, like grief, anxiety, anger, and fear, etc.^{4,14}, or affected by Infi'ālāt badaniyya, for instance, Riyadat (exercise), Istifrāgh (evacuation), Warm (swelling), Tukhma (indigestion), and sudda (obstacle).^{11,21,48} The effect can be immediate or delayed, for instance, sun exposure, hot baths, the use of Hārr (hot) medicines or Hārr (hot) food, etc. This is called the bilfail (direct) effect.

A few things exhibit indirect effect on the human body, e.g., bathing with water that contains medicines (alum water, ral water), and a cold water bath 0%. This water tightens the pores, thus fuzla dukhaniya gets pent up within the body. Because of this, body heat increases.^{3,30,31,4} Unani doctors have categorized hummā al-yawm based on cause as:

Types of Humma al-yawm

1. Humma al-yawm according to the Infi'ālāt Nafsāniyya; e.g., sadness, fear, anger, etc.
2. Humma al-yawm according to the Infi'ālāt badaniyya; e.g., Riyadat (exercise), Istifragh (evacuation), Warm (swelling), Tukhma (indigestion), and sudda (obstacle), etc.
3. Humma al-yawm according to the bilfail; e.g., sun exposure, hot baths, use of Hārr (hot) medicines or Hārr (hot) food, etc.
4. Humma al-yawm as per the bilarz; e.g., bathing with water containing medicines (alum water, ral water), and bathing with cold water, etc.

Humma 'Ufūniyya: The fever that arises due to 'ufunāt (infection) is called Humma 'Ufūniyya. 'Ufunāt (infection) of Akhlāt can give fever.^{26,41} When the hararat gharība acts upon these khilf, it gives rise to warm bukharat (vapors). The organ where these vapors collect also gets heated up. And the organ which is adjacent to it also becomes warm, one organ after another organs become hot step by step, then this heat spreads to the heart and throughout the body through blood vessels and generates fever. Fever occurs as per the Akhlāt that gets affected due to infection⁴⁸.

Humma Ufūniyya types: At times, 'ufunāt (infection) is only in one khilt²⁰.

1. Humma Mutbiqa – when 'ufunāt (infection) happens in the khilt and dam.
2. Humma Muwaziba – when 'ufunāt (infection) happens in Khilt-i-balgham.
3. Humma al-Ghibb – when 'ufunāt (infection) happens in Khilt-i-Safra.
4. Humma al-Rib – when 'ufunāt (infection) happens in Khilt Sawda.

At times, more than one khilt is affected simultaneously; the condition is then referred to as Humma murakkaba. Below are the example of Hummā murakkaba^{20,45}

1. Humma al-Ghibb and Humma al-Rib.
2. Humma al-Ghibb and Humma Muḥbiqa.
3. Humma al-Rib and Humma Muḥbiqa.
4. Rib na iba and Rib da'ima.
5. Humma Muwāziba and Humma Mutbiqa.

Humma Khiltiyya: There are four kinds of Akhlāt in the body. When any of them is infected, it results in fever, and it is named Humma Khiltiyya. It is of four kinds.

1. Humma Muḥbiqa (sanguineous fever) – The fever which occurs when 'ufunāt (infection) happens in Khilt dam intravascularly^{11,48,9,22,25,39}

2. Humma al-Ghib (tertian fever) – when ufanat (infection) happens in the Khilt Safra.
3. Humma-e-Balgamiya / humma muwāziba (quotidian fever) – when 'ufunat (infection) happens in Khilt e balgham.
4. Humma al-Rib (quotidian fever) – when 'ufūnat (infection) happens in Khilt Sawda.

Humma Mutbiqa / Humma Damwi / Tape Khūni (Sanguineous Fever)^{11, 39, 48, 3, 17}

In the human body majority of the blood is found inside the blood vessels, and a small quantity is outside the blood vessels. The hari (episode) does not take place in this fever. This fever is constant in nature.

Jalinos narrated that: Infection is not seen in the dam (blood). When hararat ghariba is applied upon it, resulting in excitement and ubal, then lateef component is altered to Şafra, and ghaleez component is altered to Sawda.¹⁴ Humma Muşbiqa results because of two reasons. The first reason is that the blood which is within and without the blood vessels becomes rotten ^{21,30}. When the infection takes place within the blood vessels, it is referred to as Humma Muşbiqa haqeeqi / Hummā Dā'ima / Tāp Muşbiqa Lazima ^{4,55}. Then harārat gharīziyya naturally attempts to liquefy it ⁴⁸. A certain quantity of infected blood is liquefied. And there is some quantity of blood that still remains infected ²². The second reason is that when the volume of blood increases and heats up within the body without infection, this fever is hummā Sünükhus.⁴²

Humma Musbiqa 'Ufuniyya Mutazā'ida: When infected blood is greater than the dissolved blood, the fever occurs persistently with strong intensity ^{4, 14, 18, 48, 22}.

Humma Mutbiqa 'Ufūniyya Mutanaqisaa: When dissolved blood is in excess of infected blood, it is strong initially, then continues decreasing gradually ^{4, 14, 18, 48, 22}.

Humma Musbiqa 'Ufūniyya Mutasawiya: When infected blood and dissolved blood are equal in

amount, it is constant from beginning to end ^{4, 14, 31, 18, 25, 22}.

Humma al-Ghibb (Tertian Fever): Inside and outside the vessels in the body, the Khilt-i-Safra exists, and it putrifies at both sites ⁴⁵. When fever results from the putrefaction of Safra, Humma al-Ghib is the condition. In Hindi, Tajari or Tiya is Hummā al-Ghib ⁶⁰.

Safra accepts the 'ufūnat (infection) or not? Safra and Sawda have a dry temperament, but at the same time, they accept infection, the things that are moist in nature, and their temperament is dry, then infection will develop in it, e.g., barg gule tar, barg murad, etc. ³¹. That's why infection occurs in Safra and Sawda. If it is dry in nature and temperament, it is not infected because it does not have rutubat, e.g., khakh shushk, chuna, etc. ²². Ibn Sina and Ibn Hubl Baghdadi explained three forms of Humma al-Ghibb ^{14, 25, 27}

1. Humma al-Ghibb Da'ira / Na'iba (bilious intermittent fever): This type of fever results from the infection of Safra outside the blood vessels, where the bout takes place every third day ^{4, 14, 42, 26}
2. Humma al-Ghibb Lazima / Da'ima (bilious continuous fever): This is the continuous fever, resulting from the infection of Safra inside the blood vessels ^{4, 14, 42, 26, 31}
3. Humma al-Ghibb Muharriqa / Hadda (high-grade bilious fever): It is a form of Hummā al-Ghibb Lazima / Da'ima. The disease occurs in the Safra, which exists in the vessels around the heart, liver, and stomach. Fever arrives with incessant high-grade temperature ^{4, 14, 42, 26, 31}.

Ibn Sina states that Humma al-Ghibb Muharriqa/Hādda is the type of Hummū al-Ghibb Lāzima. And the sole distinction is that its intervals are not perceived, and its complications are more serious. Here, the reason for the hiddat is the seriousness and excessiveness of the substance, or the infection occurring near the heart, liver, and stomach.

The Qarshi says, If the Safra is infected outside the veins and produces fever, then it is known as Ghibb Da'ira. And if it is infected outside the veins, then it

has two categories. First, if the infection is made close to the azayeraisa, such as the heart, then it is Ghibb Muharriqa. And if that is not so, then it is Ghibb Lazima²⁵. At times, the issue of these three types is solely Safrā, then it is Ghibb khalisa. And whenever there is any other khilt (balgham) blended with it, then it is Ghibb ghair khalisa^{25,31}.

Types of Hummā al-Ghibb

According to Mohd Azam Khan²⁵

1. Ghibb Da'ira Khalisa
2. Ghibb Da'ira Ghair Khalisa
3. Ghibb Lazima Khalisa
4. Ghibb Lazima Ghair Khalisa
5. Ghibb Muharriqa Khalisa
6. Ghibb Muharriqa Ghair Khalisa

According to Jurjani²²

1. Tap Khalisa
2. Ghibb Lazima
3. Shitrul Ghibb

According to Ibn Sina^{11,39}

1. Ghibb Da'ira
2. Ghibb Lazima
3. Ghibb Muharriqa
4. Shitrul Ghibb

Its contents are bile and phlegm. But these two khilts are not mixed. The two khilts are separated from each other. On the first day, the bout is more severe. And on the second day, the bout is slow and mild. Because the bout of each khilt appears separately. The fever is accompanied by a high temperature on the day of the bout owing to the Safrā. And on the day of the bout, owing to Balgham, Fever is accompanied by a low temperature^{22,31}.

Difference between the Ghibb Ghair Khalis and Shitrul Ghibb: Shitrul Ghibb includes Imtizāj Sādhij, but the two khilt are not combined. The symptoms of these khilt are appear apart. There are two episodes of Shitrul Ghibb, one due to Safra and the second due to Balgham. But in Ghibb ghair khalisa Imtizāj Haqiqi exists, there is only one episode visible because Safra and balgham, which are contained in it, are blended in a manner that these cannot be differentiated^{14,22,25}. Ibn Sina stated that, similar to **Ghibb Da'ira**, **Ghibb Muharriqa** also occurs in two forms based on the infected humour. **Muharriqa Safravi** arises when *Safra* becomes infected within the blood vessels of the entire body, particularly those of the heart, liver, and stomach. In contrast, **Muharriqa Balghami** develops when *Balgham Shor* becomes infected in the vessels situated near the heart, making the condition more severe due to its close association with vital organs.

Humma-e-Balghamiyya / Hummā Muwāziba (Quotidian Fever): Occurs when disease affects *khilt-e-balgham* and produces fever. Since balgham is present both within and outside the blood vessels, infection may arise at either site, leading to different clinical forms. This fever is broadly classified into two types: **Humma Da'ira or Humma Nā'iba (intermittent fever)** and **Humma Da'ima or Hummā Lāzima (continuous fever)**.

Humma Da'ira (Humma Nā'iba) develops due to infection of balgham located outside the vascular system, such as in the stomach, lungs, or brain. It is characterized by chills and rigor, with febrile bouts appearing on alternate days, and is commonly termed *Humma Muwāziba* in Arabic. In contrast, **Humma Da'ima (Hummā Lāzima)**, also called *Humma Lathiqa*, results from infection of balgham within the blood vessels. In this form, a persistent low-grade fever remains present continuously and closely resembles *Humma Diqqiyya*. The infection commonly involves various types of balgham, including *Balgham Zujāji*, *Tursh*, *Malih*, and *Hulw*.

Types of Humma-e-Balghamiyya

Humma Afyālūs: In this fever, the exterior of the body heats up, and the interior of the body cools down^{42,14}. This fever results from putrefaction in phlegm that already exists somewhere within the body, and when this phlegm accumulates in a place it was not

before. Thus, the body itself becomes cold, and the phlegm is viscid (ghaleez) and thick (laisdar), because of which it does not spread in the body. Thus, the outside parts are not cold. And the vapours emitted by this infected khilt do not generate heat in the outside portion of the body. In this fever, the bari appear on the third or fourth day ^{11,22,39}.

Hummā Līfuriyā: The internal body heats up, and the external body cools down in this fever ⁴². This is also due to putrefaction in phlegm, and at times due to ghaleez safrā¹⁴. When phlegm gets infected somewhere within the body, it warms the place where it is located, but its vapours are not effective in warming the external part. Because of infection, the hararat gharīziyya and quwwat enter the body to combat the infection, the outer body gets chilled ^{11,25,39}.

Humma Ghashiyya: Ghashi is ever-present in this fever. The reason for this fever is Balgham Khām, which propagates in the body and develops because of tukhma, which lowers the quwwat (quwwat e haywaniyya) of the body. Zofe Maida is due to an infection of the bladder. Due to zofe maida, loss of appetite and inappropriate digestion of food occur, and the body fails to absorb the food and get proper nutrition. Thus, the body grows weak. Hence, ghashi develops in it ^{11,25,39}.

Humma Nahariyya and Lailiyya: Hummā nahariyya is a fever, whose attack occurs during the day and continues throughout the day but ceases at night ¹⁴. The attack of Humma Lailiyya occurs at night. Humma nahariyya's matter is thicker than that of hummā lailliyya. Therefore, hummā nahariyya is more severe, and it continues for a long duration. During the day, because of the heat, the pores are still open, and the vapors also keep dissolving. Nevertheless, this fever occurs during the day because matter is stronger and in abundance. Its attacks occur daily; the patient is not permitted to sleep after supper. The quwwat weakens because of drowsiness and waking up at night. Hence, this fever is readily transformed into hummā diqqiyya ^{11,39,25}.

Humma al-Rib'

If infection happens in Khilt-e-Sawda, Khilt-e-Sawda exists within and outside the blood vessels, and 'ufunat (infection) also exists in both locations ^{45,14}.

Types of Humma al-Rib' ³⁴

1. Humma al-Rib Na'iba / Da'ira
2. Humma al-Rib' Lāzima / Da'ima

Humma al-Rib' Na'iba / Da'ira: It is also referred to as chothiyya bukhār or titrataush. It is an intermittent fever. This fever arises due to the 'ufunat (infection) of khilt-e-sawda' external to the blood vessels (lungs, stomach, etc.), where bout occurs every fourth day ^{45,42,25}. This fever develops into Waram-i-Şulb and Sartan ^{4,22,26}.

Humma al-Rib' Lāzima / Da'ima: This fever arises on account of infection of khilt-e-sawda' within vessels; in this state, fever continues perpetually ^{4,42,22,34,26,25}.

Causes of Humma al-Rib' ^{39,22}

- a) Tauleed e Sawda' (Production of Sawda' increases in the body).
- b) 'Ufunat (infection) happens in khilt-e-sawda'.
- c) Tauleed e Sawda': There are certain causes that cause an increase in the production of Sawda' in the body.
- d) Food substances, e.g., brinjal, meat, etc.
- e) Spleen weakness.
- f) Ihtiraq of dam, balgham, and Sawda' also generates Sawda.
- g) 'Ufunat (infection) in Khilt-e-Şawda ^{25,22}

When the quantity of Şawda increases in the body, hararat gharība acts upon it and leads to infection. Because of which Humma al-Rib' is generated ²⁵. This fever lasts for one year. If its matter is raw, then its duration will be longer. Istiskaa is often accompanied by this fever ²². It begins with light chills and rigors. It becomes colder later on. And then at last, the shivers cease ^{22,39}, because the matter of this fever is ghaleez and barid ^{25,22}. Through ghilzat, the body becomes

heavy, and through the coldness of the matter, it warms up gradually ^{25,22}. The body cannot warm up entirely, so it begins to grow cold again ²⁵. The vapours of sawda impact the rüh başira. Consequently, the Quwwat Başira is weakened. And the sight will be regained when the nudj happens in the matter ³⁹.

If the matter is merely Şawdā', the bari will pass in less than 24 hours. If its matter is derived from the combustion of another khilf, then the duration of its bari is shortened ²⁵. This fever generally follows other diseases and fevers. The issues of various diseases are also various, and whenever the tabiyat functions in these issues, the ghaleez matter remaining in them becomes Sawda ³⁹. Humma al-Ghib was transformed into Humma al-Rib' within a period of three months. Safra is a raqeeq khilt, which excretes from the body with sweat. And the rest of the ghaleez matter remaining in the body gets transformed into sawda'. The Humma al-Rib' are formed when there is an infection in this sawda' ²².

Humma diqqiyya

In Unani, the name of this fever is Iqtiquis ¹⁴. Diq means leanness and softness. Because this fever is rather mild and persistent. And the weakness is necessarily found in it. In this fever, the hararat gharība dissolutes body fluid ^{42,45,48,14,25,11}. Ibn Sina broadly classified body fluids into two types ^{8,37,41,58}.

Detailed Classification Chart of Each Type of Humma

This chart presents a detailed classification of each type of Humma (fever) described in Unani medicine, along with their causes and subtypes.

Main Type of Humma	Basis of Classification	Subtypes	Features/Remarks
Humma al-Yawm	External/Internal Causes	1. Infi'ālāt Nafsāniyya 2. Infi'ālāt Badaniyya 3. Bilfa'l 4. Bil'arz	Short duration; resolves in 24–72 hrs; caused by emotional or physical triggers, or hot/cold exposure
Humma Khiltiyya	Affected Humors (Akhlāt)	1. Humma Mutbiqa (Damwi) 2. Humma al-Ghibb (Safravi) 3. Humma Muwāziba (Balghami) 4. Humma al-Rib (Sawdawi)	Based on which humor is infected, intermittent or continuous fever, depending on the humor involved
Humma Ufuniyya	Infectious Disease	1. Humma Mutbiqa 2. Humma Muwāziba 3. Humma al-Ghibb	Due to ufunat (infection); can be single or mixed humor involvement.

Rufūbat Ūlā (Primary fluid) and Ruṭūbat Thaniya (Secondary fluid).

Ruṭūbat Ūla (Primary fluids): The fluid present within blood vessels with all four types of Akhlāt—Dam (blood), Safra' (yellow bile), Balgham (phlegm), and Sawda' (black bile)—is taken as the primary fluid of the body. This fluid is taken as a foundation for the remaining fluids of the body ⁵⁶.

Rububat Thaniya (Secondary fluids): The body liquids that migrate from the tissues to the spaces of the blood vessels and continue to perform the process of replenishment for the body organs. This liquid is transformed from primary to secondary fluid and is distributed into the body organs, but doesn't become practically a component of A'da Mufrada (simple organs).

This liquid is classified into four big categories ^{8,37,25,5,58}

1. Ruṭūbat Maḥşūra (Enclosed fluid/encircled fluid)
2. Ruṭūbat Talliyya (Misted fluid/interstitial fluid)
3. Ruṭūbat Qarība ba In'iqad (Nearly congealed fluids)
4. Ruṭūbat Manawiyya (Seminal fluid)

		4. Humma al-Rib 5. Humma Murakkaba	
Humma Diqqiyya	Progressive Consumption of Body Fluids	1. Diq 2. Zubul/Sill 3. Mufatit/Muhashif	Chronic fever; gradual deterioration of the body due to humoral exhaustion
Humma al-Ghibb	Safra Infection	1. Ghibb Da'ira 2. Ghibb Lazima 3. Ghibb Muharriqa 4. Ghibb Khalisa/Ghair Khalisa	High-grade or intermittent fever, depending on the infection site and Safra concentration
Humma al-Rib	Sawda Infection	1. Rib' Da'ira 2. Rib' Lazima	Usually chronic; bout every 4th day or continuous, linked with melancholic humor
Humma Muwāziba	Balgham Infection	1. Da'ira (Intermittent) 2. Lazima (Continuous) 3. Afyalus 4. Lifuriya 5. Ghashiyya 6. Nahariyya 7. Lailiyya	Mild to moderate fever; phlegmatic involvement; may cause shivering, loss of appetite, or unconsciousness.
Humma Mutbiqa	Dam Infection	1. Musbiqa Ufuniyya Mutazā'ida 2. Musbiqa Ufuniyya Mutanaqisa 3. Musbiqa Ufuniyya Mutasawiya	Continuous fever; varies with the amount of infected blood and resolution.

CONCLUSION

The study of *Humma* (fever) through the lens of Unani medicine reveals a profoundly holistic and nuanced understanding of disease pathophysiology rooted in the balance of *Harārat Gharīziyya*, *Akhlāt Arba'a*, and the regulatory role of *Tabi'at*. The detailed classification of *Humma*—*Humma al-Yawm*, *Humma Khiltiyya*, *Humma 'Ufuniyya*, and *Humma Diqqiyya*—demonstrates the diagnostic depth of classical Unani scholars like Ibn Sina, Jurjani, and Majusi. Each fever type is intricately linked to humor-specific derangements, emotional states, environmental influences, and internal pathological transformations. The recognition of infectious, temperamental, and structural causes of fever highlights the integrative nature of Unani thought, which correlates with many aspects of modern medical immunopathology and inflammation.

Therapeutically, the *Usool-e-Ilāj* principles emphasize a personalized and dynamic approach involving *Izāla-e-Sabab* (removal of cause), *Ta'dīl-e-Mizāj* (temperament correction), dietary regulations (*Ghiza*), *Tadbīr* (regimen therapy), and

pharmacological interventions aligned with *mizāj* and disease stage. The sophisticated framework of *nuzj* (ripening) and *istifrāgh* (evacuation), along with rational guidelines for cold water usage, hammam, and *fasd*, reflects a system deeply rooted in physiological observation and patient-specific management.

This research not only underscores the timeless relevance of Unani doctrines in understanding and managing febrile illnesses but also opens avenues for integrative research correlating traditional concepts with modern biomedical paradigms. In an era marked by rising infectious and inflammatory diseases, revisiting these classical insights can enrich current therapeutic frameworks and promote a more balanced, personalized model of healthcare.

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